

properties of three rice varieties (Pant Dhan 4, Pant Dhan 10, and Pant Dhan 121, collected from a university rice breeder, at 13 ± 1.00% dry basis grown in northern India. Cleaned rough rice was shelled, and unshelled ones were separated; brown rice was milled in a laboratory rice whitener (model Tm-25 Satake) for 10-110 s at 10-s intervals to attain different degrees of bran removal.

Relations between degree of polish, time of milling, milling yield, physical dimensions, and gravimetric properties were calculated by regression analysis. Only those models for which the *r* value was greater than 0.80 for linear relation were considered. The statistical results are summarized in the table. ■

Regression coefficient (*r*) and standard error of estimate (SEE) for grain characteristics with rate of bran removal. Pantnagar, India.

Grain characteristic	Pant Dhan 10		Pant Dhan 10		Pant Dhan 12	
	<i>r</i>	SEE	<i>r</i>	SEE	<i>r</i>	SEE
<i>Physical properties</i>						
Length (L)	0.700	0.200	0.690	0.060	0.650	0.057
Width (W)	0.985	0.007	0.883	0.030	0.860	0.015
Thickness (T)	0.886	0.035	0.925	0.023	0.860	0.015
Length-width ratio	0.630	0.107	0.054	0.046	0.109	0.032
Width-thickness ratio	0.693	0.020	0.550	0.027	0.969	0.009
L X W X T	0.959	0.695	0.960	0.533	0.936	0.370
<i>Gravimetric properties</i>						
Mass (M)	0.927	0.051	0.847	0.120	0.827	0.089
Bulk volume (VB)	0.915	0.177	0.942	0.111	0.841	0.279
True volume (VT)	0.810	0.149	0.841	0.141	0.936	0.049
Bulk density (DB)	0.959	0.229	0.960	0.136	0.936	0.365
True density (DT)	0.786	0.023	0.652	0.009	0.800	0.020

Effects of genotype x soil interaction on rice grain quality in japonica rice

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We evaluated quality (chemical components, texture of cooked rice, and amylogram characters) of rice grown under different conditions (soil texture, drainage, slope angle, and effective soil depth) (Table 1), using Dongjinbyeo,

the most widely cultivated variety in Korea.

The contents of Mg and Mg/K were lowest in rice grown in the Yaesan soil series, the most inferior soil. The hardness and chewiness, among textures of

cooked rice, were highest in rice grown in this same soil series. The values of maximum viscosity and breakdown were higher in rice grown in 4th class soil than those in 1st and 2nd class soils (Table 2).

Table 1. A classified standard soil class according to physical parameters for paddy field based on Korean soil series.

Soil series	Soil texture	Drainage	Slope angle (%)	Effective soil depth (cm)	Total soil class
Chonbuk	Clay-loam	Very rapid	<2	>100	1
Yongji	Clay	Rapid	2-7	50-100	2
Seongsan	Siltyclay loam	Moderate	7-15	20-50	3
Yaesan	Silt loam	Slow	>15	<20	4

Table 2. Effect of soil and environment on chemical components, texture, and amylogram characteristics of rice quality in Dongjin rice variety. Korea. 1995-96.

Soil series and location	Samples/location (no.)	Chemical component ^a							Texture of cooked rice ^a				Amylogram characters ^a			
		Amylose content (%)	Protein (%)	Fat (%)	Ash (%)	Mg (ppm)	K (ppm)	Mg/K	Hardness	Adhesive-ness	Cohesive-ness	Chewi-ness	Maximum viscosity	Minimum viscosity	Final viscosity	Break-down
Chonbuk at Iksan	9	18.4a	7.39a	1.40a	1.40a	832a	2074c	1.31a	5.78b	1.69a	0.36a	1.88b	402b	321a	571a	-169bc
Yongji at Changseong	6	17.7a	7.38a	1.40a	1.40a	840a	2173ab	1.25ab	5.17b	1.03a	0.32a	1.36b	442ab	318a	582a	-140b
Seongsan at Naju	6	17.6a	7.77a	1.43a	1.43a	837a	2137bc	1.15bc	4.85b	1.42a	0.34a	1.29b	429ab	325a	575a	-122b
Yaesan at Jeungup	6	18.0a	7.33a	1.40a	1.43a	761b	2226a	1.01c	9.14a	1.34a	0.36a	2.37a	484a	337a	564a	- 80a

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

The results indicate that chemical properties of rice grain, particularly Mg content, and Mg/K were higher in favorable soil types than in unfavorable ones where the plants grow more slowly. Some characters related to cooking quality, however, could be reversed because the starch tissue of grain produced under an inferior soil class may be caused by slow translocation and by insufficient nutrient uptake of plants. ■

Yield potential

An assessment for yield estimation in upland rainfed ecosystem of Bastar Plateau Zone, Madhya Pradesh

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The relation between grain yield and yield components can be expressed as Grain yield (g m^{-2}) = No. panicles m^{-2} \times no. spikelets panicle $^{-1}$ \times % fertile spikelets panicle $^{-1}$ \times weight of single spikelet (g) (De Datta 1981, Arraudeau and Vergara 1988). This formula does not hold well for rainfed upland rice when the paired t test is applied. Therefore I attempted various multiplication factors and finally ended up with 0.5, as described in this note. A complete block design with three replications was used during the wet seasons (WS) of 1992 and 1993, with 26 and 21 entries, respectively. They were direct-seeded (10 g m^{-2} in eight plots, 4 m in length, with 25-cm row spacing. The soil was low in available N and P_2O_5 and medium in available K_2O (220.0, 9.6, and 220.0 kg ha^{-1}) at pH 5.6. A dose of 40-8.8-8.3 kg NPK ha^{-1} was applied. Five plants were randomly selected from each plot to record observations on a randomly selected 1-m^2 area (Tables 1 and 2). Grain yield was estimated by substituting the yield attributes in the conventional and a modified formula for all the genotypes. Paired t tests for observed grain yield

Table 1. Yield attributes and estimated grain yield of extra early and early rice genotypes under upland rainfed ecosystem. Bastar Plateau Zone, Madhya Pradesh, India. 1992 WS.

Genotype	Panicles m^{-2} (no.)	Filled spikelets panicle $^{-1}$ (no.)	Spikelet fertility (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (g m^{-2})	Estimated grain yield (g m^{-2})	
						Conventional	Modified
R281 PP31-1	295	53.5	80.7	24.0	126.3	305.5	152.7
R302-111	262	58.5	73.3	24.0	132.0	269.5	134.8
JR80-4-6	342	40.9	81.4	19.4	100.7	221.0	110.5
JR82-10	322	46.5	73.0	23.3	122.0	254.6	127.3
JR84-7-1-19	270	51.2	77.8	28.1	187.7	302.1	151.0
RWR78-71-9	387	41.7	79.0	82.8	142.0	290.5	145.2
RNR-1446	341	40.7	89.9	22.7	158.3	283.6	141.8
CR92-65	260	52.9	83.6	26.3	152.0	302.7	151.0
Vanprabha	217	45.1	77.2	25.0	107.2	189.1	94.5
Heera	281	46.3	69.8	22.4	140.8	203.5	101.7
Poorva	339	46.7	76.3	26.8	129.6	323.5	161.8
Kalinga 3	362	44.5	81.7	23.8	167.3	312.9	156.5
Tulasi	348	52.1	82.0	24.8	152.5	368.5	184.2
Annada	340	57.5	81.3	26.9	177.6	427.4	213.7
Jawahar 75	322	48.4	77.6	22.7	156.0	272.6	136.3
RR180-1	263	48.9	79.4	26.5	166.0	270.7	135.4
RR51-1-1-7	274	41.3	76.0	25.0	162.3	214.9	107.5
RR151-3	301	42.5	86.7	24.7	159.3	274.1	137.0
Aditya	272	40.2	81.4	28.6	176.3	254.5	127.2
Rasi	345	46.0	80.6	22.0	138.3	281.4	140.7
Tellahamsa	339	51.3	82.6	23.7	182.7	340.8	170.4
B3619C-PB8	302	69.5	87.1	23.4	156.7	428.1	214.0
Kakudo	290	48.6	80.4	21.8	158.7	246.9	123.5
Palsul	254	80.7	86.1	19.5	177.6	344.1	172.0
Badoldhan	217	86.8	86.9	26.2	203.7	429.2	214.6
Bhilaimuch	321	79.8	85.3	9.8	115.0	214.2	107.1
Mean	302	52.4	80.6	23.6	151.9	293.3	146.6
CD (0.05)	89.3	10.9	5.2	2.8	-	-	-
t value	-	-	-	-	-	12.9	0.96
Goodness of fit	-	-	-	-	-	***a	ns ^b

^a*** = significant, $p=0.01$. ^bnonsignificant.

Table 2. Yield attributes and estimated grain yield of extra early and early rice genotypes under upland rainfed ecosystem. Bastar Plateau Zone, Madhya Pradesh, India. 1993 WS.

Genotype	Panicles m^{-2} (no.)	Filled spikelets panicle $^{-1}$ (no.)	Spikelet fertility (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (g m^{-2})	Estimated grain yield (g m^{-2})	
						Conventional	Modified
R281 PP31-1	275	63.1	83.2	24.1	140.4	347.9	173.9
JR80-4-6	289	66.4	85.8	22.7	204.6	373.6	186.8
JR82-1-10	309	68.4	80.4	27.2	253.4	459.6	229.8
JR84-7-1-19	279	71.1	83.2	27.8	283.4	459.3	229.7
RWR78-71-9	335	64.3	84.0	24.0	257.9	434.6	217.3
RR149-177	274	51.8	85.6	24.3	168.4	295.4	147.7
RR151-3	236	68.1	85.4	27.9	205.9	382.9	191.2
RR166-645	256	74.5	82.9	28.5	230.4	450.9	225.5
RR180-1	213	63.0	87.9	29.4	227.1	347.2	173.6
Kalinga 3	294	60.6	80.7	24.8	165.4	356.1	178.0
Annada	272	76.2	88.9	27.6	285.4	509.3	254.6
Poorva	260	51.0	82.1	27.9	138.4	303.7	151.8
Aditya	306	60.6	88.7	29.6	189.1	487.3	243.6
Tulasi	268	69.9	90.0	25.4	270.4	428.6	214.3
Rasi	305	67.1	87.3	24.1	250.9	430.4	215.2
Tellahamsa	283	67.0	88.2	26.1	255.4	436.9	218.4
RNR1446	298	64.9	89.1	25.2	226.6	434.5	217.3
Badoldhan	199	79.0	90.5	28.2	197.5	401.1	200.5
IR55423-15	191	83.3	86.2	27.9	192.9	382.5	191.2
TRC87-2-51	274	86.9	86.5	21.5	257.1	442.6	221.3
CR692-600	242	81.9	88.5	26.5	232.1	465.2	232.6
Mean	269	68.5	85.9	26.2	218.0	415.0	207.6
CD (0.05)	70	16.2	4.8	2.4	-	-	-
t value	-	-	-	-	-	16.2	1.45
Goodness of fit	-	-	-	-	-	***a	ns ^b

^a***=significant, $p=0.01$. ^bnonsignificant.